

HEALTHY SLEEP FOR HEALTHY KIDS!

Sleep Hygiene is choices we make that will help us to get healthy sleep

Why is sleep hygiene important to know?

Knowing what could help us sleep better and what could make it more difficult for us allows students to choose what to do and what to avoid in order to get the best and the right amount of sleep for them at the right time for them.

(photo: Uganda bedkit)

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Canadian Sleep Society Société Canadienne du Sommeil

Habits that help us fall asleep and wake up at the right time:

- ✓ Going to bed at the same time every night
- ✓ Waking up at the same time every morning
- ✓ Exercising in the early part of the day
- ✓ Relaxation or relaxing activities before bedtime
- ✓ Keeping cool
- ✓ Only getting in bed when tired or sleepy
- ✓ Getting out of bed if unable to sleep for 20 minutes

(Photo: Honduras bedkit)

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Habits that make it difficult for us to get good sleep at the right time for us:

- ☒ Going to bed and waking up at different times every night or almost every night
- ☒ Going to bed very late and waking up very late on the weekend
- ☒ Taking long naps in the afternoon/evening
- ☒ Exercising near bedtime
- ☒ Using electronics or watching TV right before bed
- ☒ Having an argument or intense argument before bed
- ☒ Drinking tea, cola, coffee or energy drinks in the evening as they contain caffeine. Caffeine is a stimulant - it wakes you up and can make it more difficult to sleep if consumed close to bedtime

(Photo: Honduras bedkit)

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*Bedkit definition: locally sourced items geared for the child's wellbeing, comprised of sleeping items (including mosquito net), clothing, and school supplies.

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